

Full Length Research Paper

Effects of Storage on Physical and Viscoelastic Properties of Yam Tubers

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The aim of the study was to evaluate the effects of storage period on the physical and viscoelastic properties of yams (*Gbangu*, *Ogoja* and *Agboyian*) tubers. The yam tubers were stored in a ventilated hut at a temperature of $28^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $80 \pm 15\%$ relative humidity for 225 day. Using the universal testing machine, the viscoelastic properties of the yam tubers were measured two times; 0 and 225 days after storage. While the yam tubers physical characteristics were measured four times 0, 75, 150, and 225 days after storage using electronic weighing scale and digital caliper. The research results showed that storage duration had significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on the physical characteristics, (mass, length, diameter, size, surface area, sphericity, and shape) of the yam tubers. Their values declined monotonically during storage, and the seven physical characteristics investigated in the study fit quadratic functions with high coefficient of determination ($R^2 \geq 0.94$). The slight variation in sphericity with storage is an indication that shrinkage is not isometric. *Gbangu* tuber sphericity decreased from 39.02 to 36.69%, *Ogoja* tuber decreased from 38.23 to

36.14%, while *Agboyian* tuber decreased from 49.75 to 46.10%. During storage, *Agboyian* tuber shrinkage was about 42 %, *Gbangu* tuber was about 32%, *Ogoja* tuber was about 30%. In addition, storage duration had significant influence on the viscoelastic properties of the yam tubers. The constants K_1 and K_2 decreased significantly during the storage period. The lower the value of K_2 is, the higher the resistance of the yam tuber to elastic deformation. Higher value of the k_1 depicts lower force relaxation rate for yam tuber under loading. Force relaxation test are useful for estimating susceptibility of yam tubers to mechanical damage, and the results indicate that the *D alata* yam cultivar exhibited lower elasticity and viscosity than the *D rotundata*; therefore the *Agboyian* yam tubers are more prone to mechanical damage than the *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* tubers.

Keywords: *Gbangu*, *Ogoja*, *Agboyian*, physical characteristics, viscoelastic, storage

INTRODUCTION

Yam belongs to the genus *Dioscorea* (Family *Dioscoreaceae*) and is the second most important tropical root crop in West Africa, next to cassava (Opara, 1999). Some species of yam originated from Africa before spreading to other parts of the world while some originated from Asia and have spread to Africa (Hahn *et al.*, 1987). According to FAO statistics, 68.13 million tonnes of yams were produced worldwide in 2014, and 65.8 million tonnes (about 97%) of this were from Africa. Nigeria is the leading yam producer in Africa, with 45 million tonnes followed by Ghana (7.1 million tonnes), Côte d'Ivoire (5.8 million tonnes), and Bénin (3.2 million tonnes) (FAO, 2014).

Yam tuber has many nutritional and medicinal values.

It is rich in carbohydrate, vitamins and minerals; generally, the ash content of yam gives an indication of its mineral status (Osagie, 1992). Yam tuber contains appreciable amount of potassium, a mineral that helps to control blood pressure; therefore, it is good for people with high blood pressure (Osagie and Eka, 1998). It also contains traces of vitamin B-complex and a steroid sapogenin compound called diosgenin, which can be used as base for drugs such as cortisone and hormonal drugs (Barquar and Oke, 1977; Albrecht and McCarthy, 2006). Brown yam flour has antioxidant activity (Farombi, 1998; Farombi *et al.*, 2000) which could be utilized to stabilize bulk oils, emulsions and biological membranes against lipid peroxidation.

During storage a substantial number of physical and viscoelastic changes happen in the agricultural products in general and yam tubers in particular. These changes can meaningfully influence the quality and viability of the yam tubers. Moisture loss induces structural changes which have many negative consequences on the textural, mechanical, chemical and nutritional composition as well as the content of bioactive substances (Correia *et al.*, 2017). Respiration, transpiration and sprouting are some factors responsible for weight loss and shrinkage of agricultural products (Ikediobi and Oti, 1983), and weight loss is one of the most severe indications of yam tuber deterioration which may be due to deleterious reactions (Osuji and Umezurike, 1985; Maalekuu *et al.*, 2014).

Physical characteristics and viscoelastic properties of agricultural products are important parameters in design of harvesting, grading, transporting, processing and packaging systems (Fu *et al.*, 2014; Rafiq *et al.*, 2016). Knowledge about physical and viscoelastic properties of yam tuber at different storage period would lead to a better understanding of their characteristics providing information for their harvesting, transportation, storage and end use quality. Many researchers in literature have investigated how physical and viscoelastic properties of roots and tubers and are relevant in the design of harvesting sorting, grading, bulk handling, storage and processing systems. Relaxation time measured show how fast the material dissipates stress after receiving a sudden deformation and can be used to characterize the elastic and viscous parts in the behavior of a material (Bargale-Praveen *et al.*, 1995). Osunde and Orhegba, (2009) studied physical and other nutritional parameters yams stored in different conditions, and their result shows losses in mass and other nutritional parameters after six months of storage. Singh *et al.*, (2006) investigated some cultivars of India potatoes *Kufri Jyoti* and *Kufri Sinduri*, and recorded declined in sphericity from 11.1 to 3.70% during 22 weeks cold storage. Aluko and Koya, (2006), studied physical and mechanical properties of yam setts during, and found out that the yam setts's density increased from 1020 and 1180 kgm⁻³ during storage. Rheological data are required for process engineering analyses, quality control and shelf-life estimation, texture evaluation, product development, and the development of constitutive equations for rheological characterization (Ofoli, 1990). Despite all of these research accounts, and increase in yam production in Nigeria, mostly production for export, there is still dearth of information on the physical and viscoelastic properties of yam tubers, which are helpful in modifying and designing sorting, handling and storage systems. Therefore, the objectives of this study is to evaluate the physical and viscoelastic properties of some yam tubers (cv. *Gbangu*, *Ogoja* and *Agboyian*) grown in Nigeria with respect to storage period, and to determine whether these properties significant correlation with storage duration. The results obtained would help in the design and development of

yam harvesting, handling and processing machines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection and storage

Three popular cultivars of yams cultivated in Nigeria were used in this study. Their local names were used to denote them, namely; *Dioscorea rotundata* (*Gbangu* and *Ogoja*), and *Dioscorea alata* (*Agboyian*), were harvested from Benue state of Nigeria. Healthy yam tubers samples selected randomly based on uniformity of shape and size and absence of bruises were cleaned by soft brush, to remove foreign materials that can encourage deterioration during storage. The cleaned yam tubers were stored inside a well-ventilated local brick hut at a temperature of 28°C ± 5°C and 80± 15% relative humidity for a period of 225 days. The temperature and relative humidity were measured four times a week and three times a day (0600 h, 1200 h and 1800 h). Temperature and humidity readings were taken using a digital thermo-hygrometer, and readings were taken at two different locations inside the hut. At each precise experimental dates (0, 75, 150, and 225 days), selected yam tubers were safely transported from Benue state to the material testing laboratory of National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, (NCAM), Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria for the viscoelastic test. During the determination of the physical parameters, all the tubers were visually examined for rot development and all the rotten tubers were recorded and discarded.

Determination of physical characteristics

The physical characteristics of the yam tubers were determined to assess their trend during storage duration. Thirty yam tubers were randomly selected and clearly marked at harvest day (0 day) and stored, but only twenty tubers results were taken at the end of storage (225 days), due to decay of some tubers during storage.

Mass determination

Unit mass of the tuber was determined by direct measurement using an electronic digital weighing balance with accuracy of 0.01g. The cumulative losses in mass were calculated as percent of initial mass lost (Moalemiyan and Ramaswamy, 2012), using equation 1.

$$M_L\% = \frac{M_0 - M_i}{M_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where

ML = Mass lost (%)

Mi = Final mass (kg)

M0 = Mass on the first day of storage (kg)

Size and shape determination

Length and diameter

To determine the length and diameter of the yam tuber, measurement of the two linear dimensions, namely length (L) and Diameter (D), of each tuber as shown in (Figure 1) were measured by using a digital caliper with accuracy of 0.01 mm.

Figure 1. Representation of the two axial forces (F_x and F_y) and two perpendicular dimensions of yam tuber.

Geometric mean diameter (size)

The geometric mean diameter (D_g), (also expressed as size ‘S’), of the yam tuber was calculated by the following relationship expressed in equation 2 (Razavi *et al.*, 2009).

$$D_g = \sqrt[3]{LD^2} \tag{2}$$

Where

- D_g =Geometric mean diameter (mm)
- L =Length of the tuber (mm)
- D =Diameter of yam tuber (mm)

Surface area

Surface area, (S_A), is defined as the total area over the outside of the yam tuber. Surface area was theoretically calculated as apparent surface area using equation 3 (Razavi *et al.*, 2009).

$$S_A = \pi D_g^2 \tag{3}$$

Sphericity

The sphericity, is defined as the ratio of surface area of a sphere having the same volume as that of tuber to the surface area of the tuber, was determined using the formula shown in equation 4 (Mohsenin, 1986).

$$\Phi = \frac{\sqrt[3]{LD^2}}{L} \times 100 \tag{4}$$

Shrinkage

Lateral and longitudinal shrinkage, S_{KG}, (%), which is the decline in surface area of the yam tuber during storage was obtained by using the formula given by Hafezi *et al.* (2015) as presented in equation 5.

$$S_{KG} = \left(1 - \frac{S_{A1}}{S_{A0}}\right) \times 100 \tag{5}$$

Force relaxation test

Since the actual surface area under an applied force continually changes with compression of roots, tubers and fruits, their true stress values are not known (Khazaei and Mann, 2004). Therefore, force relaxation of the yam tuber was evaluated instead of true stress relaxation. The force relaxation test was conducted by application of a step deformation (10%, 12.5% and 15% of the sample diameter) using the Universal Testing Machine (Testometric model, series 500-532) equipped with a 50 Newton compression load cell and integrator, at a cross head speed of 50 mm/min as recommended by Judith, (2004). The yam tuber was compressed to the required deformation (10%, 12.5% and 15%) and was then held constant; the reaction force was recorded for 4 min at 30 seconds intervals. The decay parameters calculated as normalized force and fitted to the Peleg and Norman model (Burbubai *et al.*, 2009). Compression was limited to upper limit of 15 % deformation to avoid total failure of the sample during the test. The experiment was replicated three times at each deformation level for each yam cultivar.

Following previous studies, the relaxation time F(t) = was determined using equation 6 (Mouquet *et al.*, 1992; Alvarez and Canet, 2000; Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2006).

$$F(t) = \left(\frac{F_0}{F_0 - F_\infty}\right) \tag{6}$$

$\left(\frac{F_0}{F_0 - F_\infty}\right) t$ versus time was plotted, the relaxation time was

determined and from the intercept and other stress relaxation model parameters such as initial stress, decay stress and specific viscosity were determined. For the model presented by Peleg and Normand and presented in the equation 7 (Steffe, 1996) constants k₁ and k₂ can be determined.

$$\left(\frac{F_0}{F_0 - F_\infty}\right) t = K_1 + K_2 t \tag{7}$$

Where: K₁ and K₂ are constants from the linear graph obtained by applying Excel s offtware; K₁ is the intercept

and K_2 is the slope of the Normalized straight line joining the maximum compression force and relaxed force points at 4 min. According to (Steffe, 1996) and Bhattacharya *et al.* (2006), K_1 is the initial decay rate and K_2 is the hypothetical value of the asymptotic normalized force.

Statistical analysis

For the physical characteristics, the samples were selected randomly and the measurements were done on 20 replications, on each yam cultivar. A 3 x 3 x 2 factorial experiment in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) was employed to study the effects of storage duration on viscoelastic properties of yam tubers. Three cultivars, three compression levels, and two storage duration were the considered experimental factors which were replicated three times. The data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Statistics (SPSS version 20). Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to compare the means at 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$). The constants were obtained from the intercept and slope of the relaxation curves by Microsoft Excel software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical characteristics of the yam tubers

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the physical characteristics of the yam tuber is presented in (Table 1). The results obtained show that yam cultivar and storage duration had significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on its mass, length, diameter, size, sphericity, surface area and shrinkage, Interaction of yam cultivar and storage duration still had significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on all the properties apart from its length and sphericity (Table 1). The mean values of the physical characteristics are presented in (Table 2), which shows decline in the physical characteristics during storage. While (Table 3) summarized the regression equations for the results, the relating coefficients of determination (R^2) and correlation (r) of the physical characteristics of yam tubers to storage duration. The high correlation values ($r < 0.94$) indicated a strong correlation between storage duration and the physical parameters of all the three yam cultivars investigated.

Effect of storage duration on the mass of the yam tubers

The mass of the three yam cultivars decreased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) during storage, but varied depending on the yam cultivar as presented in (Figure 2). The ANOVA results (Table 1) shows that there was a high significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the values of

mass loss at four levels of storage, three cultivar levels and their interactions. This means that the increase in storage duration affected the mass of the tuber. The differences in the losses of mass may be attributed to different rate of transpiration among the yam cultivars. Breathing, transpiration and sprouting activities of yam tuber after the harvest lead to dehydration and therefore weight loss (Ozturk and Polat, 2006; Serge and Agbor-Egbe, 1996). Mass loss that occurred at the yam cultivars at the end of storage period was 62% for *Agboyian*, followed by *Ogoja* (47.10%) and *Gbangu* (46.29%). The high mass lost in *Agboyian* tuber may be attributed to the high moisture content, which was lost to the surrounding during storage. A similar decreasing trend during storage had been reported by most previous researchers such as Osunde and Orhevba, (2009) for *Giwa* cultivar of *Dioscorea rotundata*, Maalekuu *et al.*, (2014) for *Pona* and *Tela* yam tuber, and Serge and Agbor-Egbe, (1996) for *D. rotundata* cv. *Oshei* and *D. dumetorum* cv *Jakiri*. Mass loss from yam tuber is an important physical change that occurs during storage, which affects its marketability.

Effect of storage duration on the yam tuber dimensions

The dimensions of the lengths and diameters of the yam tubers decreased as the storage duration increased from 0 day to 225 days, in the three yam cultivars (Table 2). The length of *D. rotundata* yam cultivars was longer than the *D. alata* cultivar at harvest day, and maintained this trend till the end of storage. It was also observed that the *Agboyain* tuber dimensions diminished highest than *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* tubers during storage. Regression analysis was performed on the tuber dimension as a function of storage duration, using SPSS for Windows. The results showed that the dimensions are strongly related to storage duration (Table 3). This observation conforms to findings on previous works carried out on *D. rotundata* tubers stored for 22 weeks by Ezeike, (2006).

Effect of storage duration on the yam tuber size

The results of the study show that the size of yam tuber decreased with increased in storage period, probably due to shrinkage in the tuber's dimensions during storage. Values of the yam tuber size in (Table 2) show that yam tuber diminished in size, as storage progresses. This would imply while stored yam tuber under ambient condition is expected to be accompanied with shrinkage in size and mass. At harvest, the *Agboyian* cultivar was the largest sized compared to *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* cultivars (Table 2), but as the storage duration increased, the tubers size diminished fastest than the other two cultivars, thereby, having the lowest value at the end of

Table 1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the effect of cultivar and storage duration on the physical characteristics of the three yam cultivars.

Source	Diameter	Length	Sphericity	Mass lost	Size	Surface area	Shrinkage
C	2.46E-89*	8.24E-18*	4.09E-40*	2.26E-14*	3.45E-10*	7.77E-11*	1.34E-27*
D	3.24E-102*	2.62E-06*	3.36E-02*	7.60E-77*	2.27E-58*	1.18E-58*	6.08E-107*
C x D	5.97E-19*	0.9917 ^{ns}	0.83643 ^{ns}	1.81E-12*	2.38E-04*	8.96E-06*	3.10E-09*

* =Significant on the level of 95%, ns= non significant, C = cultivar D = Storage duration

Table 2. The physical characteristics of the three yam cultivars during storage.

Properties	Storage (Days)	Yam Cultivars						
		Gbangu		Ogoja		Agboyian		
Mass (kg)		N	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
	0	20	2.68 ^d	0.29	2.62 ^d	0.33	3.58 ^d	0.46
	75	20	2.15 ^c	0.30	2.15 ^c	0.25	2.58 ^c	0.37
	150	20	1.77 ^b	0.31	1.75 ^b	0.27	1.87 ^b	0.24
	225	20	1.44 ^a	0.27	1.39 ^a	0.29	1.38 ^a	0.26
Length (mm)	0	20	375.88 ^c	39.97	366.93 ^c	59.48	316.33 ^c	46.78
	75	20	363.43 ^{bc}	37.94	355.78 ^{bc}	60.05	292.62 ^{bc}	45.33
	150	20	343.54 ^{ab}	40.80	341.54 ^{ab}	60.75	277.83 ^{ab}	38.56
	225	20	332.89 ^a	46.09	327.60 ^a	58.64	260.58 ^a	36.67
Diameter (mm)	0	20	91.44 ^d	1.46	85.61 ^d	1.48	109.76 ^d	2.89
	75	20	86.28 ^c	3.20	81.94 ^c	1.33	97.16 ^c	3.85
	150	20	79.06 ^b	2.83	76.45 ^b	2.14	89.10 ^b	3.23
	225	20	72.96 ^a	3.69	69.61 ^a	2.06	80.64 ^a	5.73
Sphericity (%)	0	20	39.02 ^b	2.91	38.23 ^b	4.14	49.75 ^b	5.39
	75	20	38.38 ^{ab}	3.07	37.96 ^{ab}	4.32	48.37 ^{ab}	5.52
	150	20	37.66 ^{ab}	3.31	37.32 ^{ab}	4.68	47.15 ^{ab}	4.93
	225	20	36.59 ^a	3.94	36.66 ^a	3.31	46.10 ^a	5.78
Size (mm)	0	20	145.58 ^d	6.06	137.99 ^d	7.90	155.02 ^d	8.12
	75	20	138.47 ^c	6.04	132.63 ^c	7.84	139.22 ^c	8.25
	150	20	128.17 ^b	6.04	124.86 ^b	7.81	129.22 ^b	6.42
	225	20	120.15 ^a	7.49	115.63 ^a	7.00	118.23 ^a	6.24
Surface area (mm ²)	0	20	66702 ^d	5469	60016 ^d	6856	75699 ^d	7864
	75	20	60351 ^c	5245	55450 ^c	6557	61100 ^c	7103
	150	20	51725 ^b	4879	49166 ^b	6162	52590 ^b	5115
	225	20	45528 ^a	5609	42158 ^a	5039	44037 ^a	4610
Shrinkage of surface area (%)	0	20	0.00 ^a	0.00	0.00 ^a	0.00	0.00 ^a	0.00
	75	20	9.49 ^b	3.24	7.62 ^b	2.25	19.34 ^b	3.33
	150	20	22.42 ^c	4.07	18.12 ^c	3.10	30.39 ^c	4.05
	225	20	31.76 ^d	6.09	29.01 ^d	11.13	41.55 ^d	5.88

\bar{x} = means, S = standard deviation, N = replication

Means values in the same rows followed by the same common letters superscript for a particular measurement are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

tubers by Tabatabaeefar, (2002) and Golmohammadi *et al.*, (2008). Such decrease in size with storage is important factor to be considered in the design of yam tuber sorting and processing machineries.

Effect of storage duration on the yam tuber surface area and shrinkage

During storage, the surface area of the yam tuber shrunk non-linearly in the three yam cultivars (Figure 3).

Shrinkage was about 42 % for *Agboyian*, 32 % for *Gbangu* and 30 % *Ogoja* respectively; therefore *Agboyian* tuber cannot undergoes long-term storage. The high level of shrinkage of *Agboyian* tuber can be attributed to its high moisture, which is lost to the environment during storage, leading to reduction in its dimension and size. Shrinkage during storage has been reported by many researchers (Peer *et al.*, 2015; Ali *et al.*, 2017), who reported a progressive shrinkage of potatoes tubers during storage. It was clearly shown that mass loss and shrinkage are major postharvest problems

Table 3. Regression equations representing the relationship between storage period and some physical characteristics of three cultivars of yam tubers.

Physical parameters	Yam cultivar	Regression Equation	R ²	r
Mass Loss (%)	<i>Gbangu</i>	$M_L = -0.0003 x^2 + 0.2784 x + 0.1605$	0.9996	0.9934
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$M_L = 0.2087 x + 1.174$	0.9960	0.9980
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$M_L = -0.0006 x^2 + 0.4007 x + 0.249$	0.9994	0.9900
Length	<i>Gbangu</i>	$L = -0.2427 x + 314.15$	0.9899	-0.9934
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$L = -0.1763 x + 367.8$	0.9971	-0.9986
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$L = -0.1985 x + 376.26$	0.9869	-0.9949
Diameter	<i>Gbangu</i>	$S_D = 5E-05 x^2 + 0.0811 x - 0.1745$	0.9974	0.9981
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$S_D = 0.0002 x^2 + 0.0462 x - 0.0285$	0.9999	0.9913
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$S_D = -0.0002 x^2 + 0.1536 x + 0.2255$	0.9973	0.9940
Sphericity (%)	<i>Gbangu</i>	$\phi = -1E-05 x^2 - 0.007 x + 39.012$	0.9995	-0.9952
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$\phi = -4E-05 x^2 - 0.0001 x + 38.222$	0.9994	-0.9590
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$\phi = 1E-05 x^2 - 0.0195 x + 49.751$	1	-0.9982
Geometric diameter (mm)	<i>Gbangu</i>	$D_g = -4E-05 x^2 - 0.1064 x + 145.85$	0.9960	-0.9977
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$D_g = -0.0002 x^2 - 0.0611 x + 138.04$	0.9998	-0.9933
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$D_g = 0.0002 x^2 - 0.2086 x + 154.68$	0.9969	-0.9945
Surface area (mm ²)	<i>Gbangu</i>	$D_g = 0.0069 x^2 - 97.744 x + 66938$	0.9958	-0.9979
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$D_g = -0.1085 x^2 - 55.392 x + 60065$	0.9997	-0.9957
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$D_g = 0.2687 x^2 - 198.46 x + 75393$	0.9966	-0.9899
Yam surface shrinkage	<i>Gbangu</i>	$S_{KG} = -7E-06 x^2 + 0.1458 x - 0.3514$	0.9958	0.9978
	<i>Ogoja</i>	$S_{KG} = 0.0001 x^2 + 0.0973 x - 0.1249$	0.9993	0.9969
	<i>Agboyian</i>	$S_{KG} = -0.0004 x^2 + 0.2628 x + 0.4209$	0.9962	0.9892

Figure 2. Interactive effects of storage duration and cultivar on yam tuber mass. Different letters on the same lines represent statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) using Duncan's multiple range test.

affecting the investigated yam tubers during storage duration. Area of tuber is often required in the design of cold storage facility, as it helps to estimate the total amount of heat and mass exchange from the tuber (Golmohammadi *et al.*, 2008). Shrinkage was found to be an important factor causing change in most of the physical characteristics investigated in this research.

Effect of storage duration on the yam tuber sphericity

The sphericity of the yam tuber decreased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) when the storage duration increased from 0 day to 225 days (Figure 4). As the storage duration increased, the sphericity of the yam tuber diminished from 39.02 to 36.69% for *Gbangu*, 38.23 to 36.14% for

Figure 3. Interactive effects of storage duration and cultivar on yam tuber shrinkage. Different letters on the same lines represent statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) using Duncan's multiple range test.

Figure 4. Interactive effects of storage duration and cultivar on yam tuber sphericity. Different letters on the same lines represent statistical differences ($p \leq 0.05$) using Duncan's multiple range test.

Ogoja and 49.75 to 46.10% for *Agboyian* respectively. The reason of this could be explained as follows: while the yam tuber loss moisture, their individual length and breadth decreases; consequently, their shapes changes. At harvest *Agboyian* tuber had the highest sphericity value among the three cultivars, but declined fastest

than *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* cultivars as storage duration increase. The sphericity of *Agboyian*, *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* are lower than those reported by (Golmohammadi and Afkari-Sayyah, 2013) for potatoes (Cv. *Agria*, *Satina*, and *Caesar*) tubers stored for 22 weeks; and Balami *et al.* (2012) on potatoes tubers. Higher sphericity indicates

Table 4. Normalized force relaxation data for *Gbangu*, *Ogoja* and *Agboyian* yam tubers (middle section) at room temperature.

Time (s)	Storage period (Days)	Yam cultivar								
		Gbangu			Ogoja			Agboyian		
		% deformation			% deformation			% deformation		
		10%	12.5%	15%	10%	12.5%	15%	10%	12.5%	15%
$\left(\frac{F_0}{F_0 - F_\epsilon}\right)$										
0.00	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	225	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
30.00	0	237.21	230.12	215.74	253.01	230.07	201.72	286.24	283.19	238.57
30.00	225	178.18	170.42	202.38	194.02	185.25	168.97	234.72	202.81	179.66
60.00	0	453.33	422.16	310.28	371.30	336.63	313.39	461.80	442.40	403.03
60.00	225	252.90	280.45	308.77	254.52	302.21	293.12	289.06	299.54	300.57
90.00	0	654.55	613.38	444.19	495.78	432.16	430.38	602.35	602.20	529.06
90.00	225	323.67	382.75	420.00	344.71	441.26	408.90	346.54	376.84	406.15
120.00	0	832.65	790.3	558.70	618.16	522.12	542.78	746.85	743.27	674.84
120.00	225	403.78	480.77	520.80	438.33	558.13	517.59	429.89	456.77	528.07
150.00	0	966.82	944.42	668.22	736.86	677.54	654.85	883.55	877.17	799.60
150.00	225	481.97	573.65	644.55	528.35	666.46	619.55	509.38	545.38	627.17
180.00	0	1097.76	1063.69	767.94	857.70	776.84	763.04	1011.24	1012.86	926.11
180.00	225	560.00	662.34	753.57	614.81	771.53	721.59	590.74	631.46	725.92
210.00	0	1225.75	1198.55	873.26	966.81	902.66	871.28	1127.65	1153.94	1050.00
210.00	225	633.23	751.41	862.52	699.11	879.43	822.50	673.38	717.32	819.93
240.00	0	1360.00	1338.44	984.18	1078.87	1007.24	972.75	1259.45	1292.79	1175.69
240.00	225	710.04	838.79	979.56	785.73	982.47	926.69	752.31	804.96	912.46

Table 5. Values (K_1 , K_2 , and r) from plot of normalized force relaxation data against time.

Species	Cultivar	Storage (Days)	Deformation (%)	K_1	K_2	r (correlation)
<i>D. rotundata</i>	<i>Gbangu</i>	0	10.0	5.559	91.558	0.9922
		0	12.5	5.481	75.486	0.9947
		0	15.0	3.916	65.926	0.9954
		225	10.0	2.766	61.898	0.9926
		225	12.5	3.362	56.586	0.9953
		225	15	3.896	53.829	0.9971
	<i>Ogoja</i>	0	10	4.262	86.226	0.9939
		0	12.5	3.985	64.638	0.9952
		0	15	3.902	59.569	0.9964
		225	10	3.090	58.015	0.9943
		225	12.5	3.987	53.418	0.9967
		225	15	3.742	48.661	0.9971
<i>D. alata</i>	<i>Agboyian</i>	0	10	4.968	112.65	0.9915
		0	12.5	5.111	98.692	0.9942
		0	15	4.697	80.515	0.9952
		225	10	2.829	85.685	0.9854
		225	12.5	3.109	75.292	0.9913
		225	15	3.690	57.168	0.9957

easier tendency of the product to roll on any of its three axes (Bamgboye and Sadiiku, 2015). Therefore, Agboyain tubers have the highest tendency to roll about any of the axes than the *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* tubers. Sphericity is an important parameter used in the design of sorting machineries. The relationship between sphericity and storage duration are represented in the regression equations in (Table 3).

Shelf life of yam tuber is mostly influenced by dormancy period, which is the period during which the tuber retains all its food quality characteristics. The breaking of dormancy is signaled by sprouting, and signals the commencement of physiological changes within the tuber arising from sprouting and respiration, which lead to the loss of food quality characteristics (Frank and Kingsley, 2013). Causes of storage losses of

yam tubers include sprouting, transpiration, respiration, rot due to mould and bacteriosis, insects, nematodes and mammals (Passam *et al.*, 1978). Variability in the duration of dormancy has been attributed to differences in species, variety crop management, data of tuber harvest, growth, and storage (Hamadina and Asiedu, 2015). Several researchers (Sparks, 1973; Ikediobi and Oti, 1983; Karadoğan, 1994; Kara, 1999) investigated the storage duration dependence of physical characteristics of roots and tubers (potatoes and yam) and reported that weight and other physical characteristics losses occurred along the storage, and varied depending on extension of storage period, relative humidity ratio, transpiration, and moisture content. Shrinkage was found to be the main reason for change in most of the physical characteristics investigated in this research.

Force relaxation

The normalized experimental data for the force relaxation test (Table 4) revealed that yam tuber behaves in a similar way as other viscoelastic materials. The results in (Table 5) represents the summary of the plot of normalized force relaxation data against time, and the values indicated that *D. rotundata* cultivars exhibit higher initial load, decay constant and relaxation time than the *D. alata* cultivar.

Force relaxation pattern of the yam cultivars tuber

The relaxation force of all the three yam cultivars increased consistently and linearly (after normalization) with time over a 225 days storage period, depicting an increase in the cell turgor pressure during storage. The normalized data values (Table 4) revealed that yam tubers behave in a similar way as other viscoelastic materials. Tables 4 and 5 indicate that the *D. rotundata* (*Gbangu* and *Ogoja*) exhibits highest initial load, decay constant and relaxation time than the *D. alata* (*Agboyian*), therefore, *Agboyian* tuber exhibited lower elasticity and viscosity than the *D. rotundata* at harvest. During storage, the elasticity and viscosity of all the three yam cultivars generally increased, in conformity with previous work of Judith, (2004) and Pang and Scanlon, (1996). The maximum force required to compress the yam tuber decreased over a 225 days storage duration, which can be attributed to increasing cell turgor pressure of the tuber tissue.

The lower the value for constant K_2 , the higher the elastic properties, and higher value of the k_1 depicts lower force relaxation rate for yam tuber, therefore the yam tuber possess higher viscoelastic properties as storage period progresses (Table 5). Alvarez and Canet, (1998) reported that viscoelastic units of relaxation tests reflect the viscoelastic properties of pectic substances and hemicelluloses. Stress or force relaxation is an important criterion used in determining the susceptibility of agricultural material to mechanical damage. From the results, *Agboyian* yam tuber is more prone to mechanical damage than the *Gbangu* and *Ogoja* tubers. The results demonstrate the significance of long term storage in the determination of the visco-elastic properties of a yam tuber, and there was a strong correlation between storage duration and viscoelastic properties of yam tuber. Previous studies of (Scanlon *et al.*, 1998; Blahovec, 2003) on potatoes further confirm the force relaxation pattern of the yam tuber during storage. Pang and Scanlon, (1996) in their work found marked differences in shear and compressive moduli of potatoes, stored for ten months compared to crops stored for one month and found the latter being much stiffer and tougher. Whereas Mechanical behaviour of yam tuber parenchyma depends on one hand on the stress rate application, cell turgor,

plasma membrane permeability as well as cell wall stiffness. On the other hand, it is influenced by the ductility of the middle lamella, intercellular space and number, size and shape of cells in the plane of applied stress (Niklas, 1992).

Engineering applications

Data gotten from this research will help to understand the physical and viscoelastic characteristics of yam tubers during storage. The information obtained from this study are useful in many postharvest processes, such as; mechanical loading, sorting, handling, transportation and storage. The data gotten from this research could facilitate the design of improved storage facilities yam tubers, and the amount of vibration force the yam tubers can withstand during transportation, mostly now, Nigeria want to engage in yam exportation.

Conclusion

It was concluded that yam tuber quality is highly dependent on storage time and cultivar and declines over time. The following conclusions could be drawn from the research carried out:

- (i) Physical and Viscoelastic properties of the three yam cultivars studied are dependent on storage duration.
- (ii) The results showed that surface area reduction (shrinkage), and mass loss were highest in the *D. alata* cultivar, than those of the *D. rotundata*.
- (iii) That yam tuber had time dependent relaxation behaviour similar to other viscoelastic materials.
- (iv) Increase in storage duration caused the coefficients k_1 and k_2 of the model presented by Peleg and Normand to decrease.
- (v) The *D. rotundata* cultivars have higher resistance to elastic deformation than the *D. alata*.

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Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research that was carried out by our research team and we agreed to publish it in the journal.

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